

Atsushi Tadokoro, Conversations Beyond Code: Bridging Human Creativity and Algorithms

Live Performances (including audio, visual, and A/V or multimedia) will largely be sorted into one of two formats: a concert format, with seated audience; and an Algorave format, unseated and intended for dancing.

1. General Information

- **Performance Title:** Conversations Beyond Code: Bridging Human Creativity and Algorithms
- **Main Contact:** Atsushi Tadokoro
- **Additional Performers:**
- **Performance Type:** Algorave

2. Abstract

Conversations Beyond Code: Bridging Human Creativity and Algorithms

Live coding performances are frequently misconceived as isolated endeavors undertaken by individual programmers. In contrast to this perception, live coding transcends the boundaries of a solitary activity, encompassing a dualistic form of conversation.

The primary conversation is that which occurs between the performer and the audience. This facet has been a perennial element in conventional live performances. Distinguished performers do not merely execute their compositions mechanistically; they dynamically respond to audience feedback, improvising modifications to invigorate the ambiance. Live coding distinctively amalgamates the inherently logical coding process with the sensory elicitation of instinctual audience responses to rhythm and harmony. This amalgamation of ostensibly opposing elements renders it a sophisticated and exhilarating act.

The secondary conversation transpires between the performer and the computer, an interaction quintessential to live coding. Participation in live coding performance unveils the collaborative dimension of this human-computer interaction. The inputting and executing code frequently culminates in unforeseen musical or visual outputs. Adept live coders deftly integrate these fortuitous results into their performance, engaging in a conversation with the computer or, more precisely, with the underlying algorithms. This paradigm, intrinsic to live coding, is anticipated to evolve further with advancements in AI technologies, notably large language models (LLMs).

My live coding performances are conducted within this framework of dual conversation. I craft complex and nuanced soundscapes using TidalCycles, SuperDirt, and Ableton Live. These tools facilitate the exploration of a spectrum of auditory expressions, ranging from subtle ambient textures to complex rhythmic patterns.

Concurrent with the auditory experience, the generation of real-time visuals via TouchDesigner assumes a significant role. The synthesis of sound and visuals yields a coherent, interconnected narrative, thereby augmenting the overall impact of the performance. The seamless interaction between auditory and visual elements is achieved through Open Sound Control (OSC), which ensures a harmonized, synchronized performance. This protocol is pivotal in linking disparate applications and fostering efficacious communication.

In summation, live coding transcends mere demonstration of programming expertise, embodying a multifaceted performance art rooted in the interplay among the performer, the audience, and the computer. This evolving art form, bolstered by technological progress, continues to challenge and expand the traditional boundaries of artistic expression and audience engagement, offering opportunities to deepen audience rapport and explore new realms of creative expression.

3. Video and/or Audio Material

Performance Videos

- https://youtu.be/wgPf24_OQZY
- <https://youtu.be/w12XZ2-oqwE>

Photos

- <https://photos.app.goo.gl/sTYgWb6H8wd6awCK8>

4. Program Note

In this live coding performance, I explore the captivating contrast between the logical precision of coding and the creation of instinctive, emotional experiences. This performance goes beyond the realms of conventional coding, tapping into the primal power of rhythm and color to evoke deep emotions in the audience. I use real-time coding to generate an evolving soundscape, accompanied by visuals that dynamically respond to the music, creating a rich, multi-sensory experience.

Central to this performance is the interactive element, where audience reactions shape the flow, making each moment unique. This is not just a showcase of technical skills but a journey into the heart of artistic expression, where each line of code and every beat creates a connection between technology and emotion.

5. Artist(s) Biography

Atsushi Tadokoro

Live Coder / Creative Coder / Associate Professor at Maebashi Institute of Technology / Adjunct Lecturer at Tokyo University of the Arts / Adjunct Lecturer at Keio University. Born in 1972. He creates musical works by synthesizing sounds using algorithms and improvises with sounds and images using laptop computers. At university, he lectures on "creative coding" such as openFrameworks, Processing, and p5.js. His lecture materials are available on the website (<https://yoppa.org/>) and are used by many students and creators. He is the author of "Beyond Interaction - A Practical Guide to openFrameworks for Creative Coding" BNN 2020, "Performative Programming, The Art and Practice of Live Coding - Show us your screens." BNN 2018.